

The Impact of Work Family School Conflict on Work Stress in Doctoral Management Students at Mercu Buana University

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Article Information

Received: January 2024

Accepted: March 2024

Published: April 2024

Keywords

Work family school conflict,
Work stress

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DOI

[10.60036/ssij.v2i1.art3](https://doi.org/10.60036/ssij.v2i1.art3)

Abstract

This research is intended to see the effect of work family school conflict on work stress. The study population was 61 doctoral management students in active status who were members of the whatsapp group "UMB Management Doctoral Association". The number of samples was as large as the study population but only 39 people (63.93%) responded. Simple linear regression is used in data analysis. The result is that work family school conflict has a positive impact on work stress. Suggestions for future researchers to expand the scope of doctoral study programs at other universities. For universities, publications provide relief in carrying out campus activities. For the company, it gives tolerance to employees who are in college. For the family, they actually provide support for their families who work while studying.

INTRODUCTION

Work stress needs attention because it has developed into a major problem in the modern organizational environment and has an impact on companies and employees themselves. Work stress can make an employee feel less satisfied with their job and also make employees feel tired physically, mentally and emotionally (Wu et al., 2021). Job stress can also increase intentions to change jobs (Fasbender et al., 2019), reducing employee performance (Durrab Hussain et al., 2019), increases the likelihood of a mental health diagnosis (Hege et al., 2019). Employees with high stress will have low organizational commitment (Anggreyani et al., 2020). The decrease in job satisfaction is caused by increased work stress (Salsabilla et al., 2022). School has been overlooked as a source of stress and tension due to the inevitable conflict with demanding work and family roles among married and working students (Kremer, 2016).

Work stress is influenced by various factors. Role ambiguity, underutilization of skills, too large a workload are factors that trigger work stress (Jalagat, 2017). Support from superiors was found to reduce work stress (Hoboubi et al., 2017). Workers with large psychological capital will have little work stress (Abbas & Raja, 2015). Interventions in the form of mental health promotion programs in the workplace can reduce work stress, physical and mental reactions, reduce work absenteeism, improve performance and social support (Ornek & Esin, 2020).

Emotional intelligence was found to be able to reduce work stress (Karimi et al., 2014).

One of the factors that can influence work stress in working students is the conflict that occurs between work, family and study. Conflicts that occur due to work interfering with family relationships can increase employee work stress (Nart & Batur, 2014). Conflicts that occur because school activities interfere with work can cause stress (Kremer, 2016). *Work family school conflict* secara positif terkait dengan kelelahan mahasiswa, stres sekolah, stres pekerjaan dan gejala depresi (Oviatt et al., 2017). Tension, work-to-family conflict, family-to-work conflict are significantly related to job stress and job satisfaction (Armstrong et al., 2015).

Pressure between work and school time predicts higher school-work conflict (Wan et al., 2021). Conflict between work and school is able to predict work outcomes but depends on the level of fatigue felt (Laughman et al., 2016). Healthy emotional regulation capacity can reduce the impact of conflict between work, school and family (Suh et al., 2022). Conflict between family and school, conflict between school and work can predict well-being (Koh & Farruggia, 2023).

This research aims to determine the extent to which work family school conflict influences work stress in management doctoral students. So far, no research has been found in Indonesia regarding the impact of work family school conflict on work stress for doctoral students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Stress

Stress is an aspect that will always be present in human life in the form of mental pressure or as a physiological response to threatening environmental stimuli (Mohammadi et al., 2020). Stress is associated with many diseases and is an important reason for absenteeism in healthcare organizations. This occurs when workers' expectations exceed their authority and abilities, causing personal problems, unemployment and disruption to organizational performance (Isfahani et al., 2021).

Work Family School Conflict

Current literature provides evidence that conflicts between work, family and school can have negative impacts (Olson, 2014). The development of a theoretical and empirically based measure of work-family school conflict provides researchers and practitioners with guidance in cataloging the antecedents and consequences of work-family school conflict.

Research investigating the relationship between school engagement and job performance is useful because theoretically integrating multiple roles is a complex process. Research that investigates domains other than work aspects provides insight into how each domain influences work outcomes, while large amounts of financial resources are spent on providing educational assistance on the part of employers (Wyland et al., 2013).

METHOD

This research uses a quantitative design. The research population is management doctoral students with active status at Mercu Buana University, Jakarta. This study used a saturated sample of 61 people where the sample was the same as the total population. A total of 39 filled out the questionnaire (63.93% of the population). Questionnaires were distributed via Google Form to active students who are members of the WhatsApp group "UMB Doctoral Management Association" via direct message.

The work family school conflict measuring instrument was adapted from (Olson, 2014) with a total of 36 items while the work stress measuring tool was adapted from (Shukla & Srivastava, 2016) with a total of 9 items. Work family school conflict has 12 dimensions, namely WSC (strain-based), WSC (time-based), WSC (behavior-based), SWC (strain-based), SWC (time-based), SWC (behavior-based), FSC (strain-based), FSC (time-based), FSC (behavior-based), SFC (strain-based), SFC (strain-based), SFC (strain-based). Work stress has 2 dimensions, namely time stress and anxiety.

The data analysis process uses simple linear regression with the help of SPSS software. The stages are descriptive analysis followed by validity test, reliability test, normality test, heteroscedasticity test, linearity test, t test, coefficient of determination test, correlation matrix between dimensions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Description

Demographics of research subjects or participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic description of research subjects

Category	Total	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Man	19	48.7
Woman	20	51.3
Marital Status		
Married	29	74.4
Not Married Yet	10	25.6
Length Of Work		
< 5 year	10	25.6
5 – 10 year	2	5.1
> 10 year – 15 year	6	15.4
> 15 year – 20 year	5	12.6
> 20 year	16	41
Total	39	100%

Table 1 shows a description of 39 respondents. Most respondents were female (51.3%) followed by male subjects (48.7.1%). Based on the marital status category, most of the subjects were married (74.4%) and the remainder were single (25.6%). Based on the length of work category, the majority of subjects have worked for more than 20 years (41%), the remainder have worked for less than 5 years (25.6%), have

worked for more than 10 years to 15 years (15.4%), have worked more from 15 years to 20 years (12.6%) and working 5 to 10 years (5.1%).

Validity Test

Table 2. Work Family School Conflict Validity Test Results

Indicator	R	Decision
WFSC1	0.675**	Accept
WFSC2	0.714**	Accept
WFSC3	0.794**	Accept
WFSC4	0.775**	Accept
WFSC5	0.580**	Accept
WFSC6	0.607**	Accept
WFSC7	0.812**	Accept
WFSC8	0.730**	Accept
WFSC9	0.687**	Accept
WFSC10	0.683**	Accept
WFSC11	0.667**	Accept
WFSC12	0.592**	Accept
WFSC13	0.765**	Accept
WFSC14	0.731**	Accept
WFSC15	0.464**	Accept
WFSC16	0.802**	Accept
WFSC17	0.741**	Accept
WFSC18	0.713**	Accept
WFSC19	0.714**	Accept
WFSC20	0.718**	Accept
WFSC21	0.725**	Accept
WFSC22	0.785**	Accept
WFSC23	0.794**	Accept
WFSC24	0.777**	Accept
WFSC25	0.815**	Accept
WFSC26	0.776**	Accept
WFSC27	0.759**	Accept
WFSC28	0.728**	Accept
WFSC29	0.776**	Accept
WFSC30	0.796**	Accept
WFSC31	0.755**	Accept
WFSC32	0.789**	Accept
WFSC33	0.738**	Accept
WFSC34	0.828**	Accept
WFSC35	0.807**	Accept
WFSC36	0.727**	Accept

** Valid with a significance level of 99%

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 2 shows the results of the validity test of the work family school conflict scale where the smallest validity value is in item number 15 of 0.464 while the largest validity value is in item number 34 of 0.828. In the results of the validity test, no items were dropped and this also strengthens the results of the previous validity test with a range of 0.77 to 0.97 (Olson, 2014).

Table 3. Validity of Job Stress

Indicator	R	Decision
SK1	0.656**	Accept
SK2	0.724**	Accept
SK3	0.780**	Accept
SK4	0.706**	Accept
SK5	0.834**	Accept
SK6	0.622**	Accept
SK7	0.846**	Accept
SK8	0.759**	Accept
SK9	0.781**	Accept

** Valid with a significance level of 99%

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 3 shows the results of the work stress scale validity test where the smallest validity value is in item number 6 of 0.622 while the largest validity value is in item number 7 of 0.846. In the results of the validity test, no items were dropped and this also strengthens the results of the previous validity test with a range of 0.760 to 0.997. (Shukla & Srivastava, 2016).

Reliability Rest

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Total Item	Cronbach Alpha
Work Family School Conflict	36	0.975
Job Stress	9	0.898

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 4 shows the results of the reliability test for the work family school conflict variable at 0.975 and the work stress variable at 0.898. Both values are > 0.6 so that the two natural measuring instruments for this research are declared reliable.

Classic Assumption Test

**Table 5. Normality Test
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test**

		Unstandardized Residual
N		39
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.00
	Std. Deviation	3.97259973
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.131
	Positive	.131

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Unstandardized Residual	
	Negative	-.106
Test Statistic		.131
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.087 ^c

a. The test distribution is normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. *Lilliefors Significance Correction.*

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 5 shows the results of the normality test with Asymp Sig values. of 0.087. If this value is greater than 0.05, the measurement results of the two variables are declared to be normally distributed.

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

	T	Sig.
<i>Work Family School Conflict</i>	0.141	0.888

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 6 shows the results of the heteroscedasticity test where the Sig value. of 0.888. If this figure is higher than 0.05, it can be concluded that the research results are free from heteroscedasticity.

Table 7. Linearity Test

	F	Sig.
<i>Deviation from Linearity</i>	1.295	0.346

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 7 shows the results of the linearity test where the deviation from linearity is 0.346. If this figure is more than 0.05, the data is linear.

Hypothesis testing

Table 8. T test

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.338	2.527		.530	.599
	<i>Work family school conflict</i>	.231	.025	.839	9.371	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Stress

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 8 shows the t test results with Sig values. of 0.000. This value is smaller than 0.05, so the research results state that work family school conflict has a significant effect on work stress. The calculated t value is 9.371 and is positive, meaning that the influence of work family school conflict is in the same direction as work stress. The standardized coefficient beta value is 0.839 and this states the

strength of the relationship between the two variables. The unstandardized coefficients beta value is 0.231, which means that if work family school conflict increases by 1 point, work stress will increase by 0.231.

Table 9. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square
1	0.839 ^a	0.704

a. Predictors: (Constant), work family school conflict

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 9 shows the results of the coefficient of determination test where the R Square value is 0.704. This value means that work family school conflict has a contribution of 70.4% to work stress while the remaining 29.6% is influenced by other factors or variables.

Table 10. Correlation Test Results Between Dimensions

Dimensions	Time Stress	Anxiety
WSC (strain based)	0.710	0.719
WSC (time based)	0.403	0.580
WSC (behavior based)	0.670	0.631
SWC (strain based)	0.578	0.564
SWC (time based)	0.636	0.566
SWC (behavior based)	0.689	0.592
FSC (strain based)	0.696	0.727
FSC (time based)	0.704	0.734
FSC (behavior based)	0.740	0.726
SFC (strain based)	0.655	0.654
SFC (time based)	0.655	0.708
SFC (behavior based)	0.728	0.690

Source: 2023 Data Processing Results

Table 10 shows the correlation matrix between dimensions where the largest value, namely 0.740, is in the relationship between the FSC (behavior based) dimension and the time stress dimension. The smallest value, namely 0.403, is in the relationship between WSC (time based) and time stress. All dimensions of work family school conflict are positively related to all dimensions of work stress.

The results of this study found that work family school conflict has a significant positive impact on work stress. When the conflict between work, family and college is low, the perceived work stress will also be lower. Several findings support the results that when school activities interfere with work activities, it can cause stress (Kremer, 2016). Conflicts that occur due to work interfering with family activities are positively related to work stress (Nart & Batur, 2014). When work interferes with school activities, it can cause negative emotions (Peng et al., 2023). Work versus school conflict was found to be positively related to burnout in working students (Park & Sprung, 2015).

Workload and work pressure are factors that give rise to work-family conflict which then increases work stress (Ilies et al., 2015; Nart & Batur, 2014). This indicates

that by reducing the burden and pressure of work, it will reduce conflicts that occur between work and family and ultimately reduce work stress for working students. School work conflict is a link to the impact of organizational support on job satisfaction (Lubis & Nurhayati, 2020). Work-school conflict is associated with lower general psychological health as well as higher school burnout (McNall & Michel, 2017). When work conflicts with study activities in high school, it can worsen health (Owen et al., 2018). An irregular work schedule triggers work-family conflict and ultimately causes poor mental and physical health (Cho, 2018).

Job stress and work-family conflict were found to be predictors of job turnover intention (Lu et al., 2017). Generational differences cause differences in levels of work-family conflict, where generation X has the highest level, followed by generation Y and the baby boom (Bennett et al., 2017).

The results of the correlation test between dimensions show that when work interferes with college activities, college interferes with work activities, family interferes with school activities, school interferes with family activities, it can increase time-related stress and anxiety.

CONCLUSION

This research concludes that work family school conflict has a significant positive effect on the work stress of management doctoral students at Mercu Buana University. All dimensions of work family school conflict are positively correlated with dimensions of work stress. This research has an impact on efforts to deal with stress in employees who are currently studying by reducing conflicts that occur in the areas of work, study and family. Companies are expected to give permission to employees who want to study and provide flexibility in work hours. Universities that hold employee class programs must also provide concessions regarding filling absences through assignments as well as extending tuition payment periods. Families must be able to understand family members who are working while studying by taking on more roles in the family.

Suggestions for future researchers to expand the population in doctoral study programs at other universities. Universities should provide relief in carrying out campus activities. Companies should tolerate employees who are studying in the form of more flexible working hours. Families should provide support for their families who work while studying.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, M., & Raja, U. (2015). Impact of psychological capital on innovative performance and job stress. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 32(2), 128–138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjas.1314>
- Anggreyani, N. M., Gustibagus, I., & Satrya, H. (2020). Effect of Job Satisfaction, Employee Empowerment and Job Stress Towards Organizational Commitment. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 6, 108–113.
- Armstrong, G. S., Atkin-Plunk, C. A., & Wells, J. (2015). The Relationship Between Work–Family Conflict, Correctional Officer Job Stress, and Job Satisfaction. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 42(10), 1066–1082.

- <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854815582221>
- Bennett, M. M., Beehr, T. A., & Ivanitskaya, L. V. (2017). Work-family conflict: differences across generations and life cycles. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 32(4), 314–332. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-06-2016-0192>
- Cho, Y. (2018). The effects of nonstandard work schedules on workers' health: A mediating role of work-to-family conflict. *International Journal of Social Welfare*, 27(1), 74–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijsw.12269>
- Durrab Hussain, S., Khaliq, A., Ali Nisar, Q., Zamir Kamboh, A., & Ali, S. (2019). Impact of Employees' Recognition, Rewards and Job Stress on Job Performance: Mediating Role of Perceived Organization Support. *SEISENSE Journal of Management*, 2(X), 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.33215/sjom.vXiX.XX>
- Fasbender, U., Van der Heijden, B. I. J. M., & Grimshaw, S. (2019). Job satisfaction, job stress and nurses' turnover intentions: The moderating roles of on-the-job and off-the-job embeddedness. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 75(2), 327–337. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13842>
- Hege, A., Lemke, M. K., Apostolopoulos, Y., & Sönmez, S. (2019). The Impact of Work Organization, Job Stress, and Sleep on the Health Behaviors and Outcomes of U.S. Long-Haul Truck Drivers. *Health Education and Behavior*, 46(4), 626–636. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1090198119826232>
- Hoboubi, N., Choobineh, A., Kamari Ghanavati, F., Keshavarzi, S., & Akbar Hosseini, A. (2017). The Impact of Job Stress and Job Satisfaction on Workforce Productivity in an Iranian Petrochemical Industry. *Safety and Health at Work*, 8(1), 67–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2016.07.002>
- Ilies, R., Huth, M., Ryan, A. M., & Dimotakis, N. (2015). Explaining the links between workload, distress, and work-family conflict among school employees: Physical, cognitive, and emotional fatigue. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107(4), 1136–1149. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000029>
- Isfahani, P., Shamsaie, M., Peirovy, S., Bahador, R. C., & Afshari, M. (2021). Job stress among Iranian nurses: A meta-analysis. *Nursing and Midwifery Studies*, 10(1), 57–64.
- Jalagat, R. (2017). Determinants of Job Stress and Its Relationship on Employee Job Performance. *American Journal of Management Science and Engineering*, 2(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajmse.20170201.11>
- Karimi, L., Leggat, S. G., Donohue, L., Farrell, G., & Couper, G. E. (2014). Emotional rescue: The role of emotional intelligence and emotional labour on well-being and job-stress among community nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 70(1), 176–186. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.12185>
- Koh, J., & Farruggia, S. P. (2023). Family-Work-School Conflicts, Self-Regulation, and Well-Being Among Transfer Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19496591.2022.2158741>
- Kremer, I. (2016). The relationship between school-work-family-conflict, subjective stress, and burnout. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 31(4), 805–819. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-01-2015-0014>
- Laughman, C., Boyd, E. M., & Rusbasan, D. (2016). Burnout as a Mediator Between

- Work–School Conflict and Work Outcomes. *Journal of Career Development*, 43(5), 413–425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845316633523>
- Lu, Y., Hu, X. M., Huang, X. L., Zhuang, X. D., Guo, P., Feng, L. F., Hu, W., Chen, L., Zou, H., & Hao, Y. T. (2017). The relationship between job satisfaction, work stress, work-family conflict, and turnover intention among physicians in Guangdong, China: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*, 7(5), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-014894>
- Lubis, F., & Nurhayati, M. (2020). Authentic Happiness As a Mediator of Learning Organization. *Dinasti International Journal Of Management Science*, 1(3), 277–293. <https://doi.org/10.31933/DIJMS>
- McNall, L. A., & Michel, J. S. (2017). The relationship between student core self-evaluations, support for school, and the work–school interface. *Community, Work and Family*, 20(3), 253–272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13668803.2016.1249827>
- Mohammadi, M., Vaisi-Raygani, A., Jalali, R., & Salari, N. (2020). Prevalence of job stress in nurses working in Iranian hospitals: a systematic review, meta-analysis and meta-regression study. *JHSW*, 10(2), 119–128.
- Nart, S., & Batur, O. (2014). The relation between work-family conflict, job stress, organizational commitment and job performance: A study on turkish primary teachers. *European Journal of Research on Education*, 2(2), 72–72. <https://doi.org/10.15527/ejre.201426250>
- Olson, K. J. (2014). Development and initial validation of a measure of work, family, and school conflict. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 19(1), 46–59. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034927>
- Ornek, O. K., & Esin, M. N. (2020). Effects of a work-related stress model based mental health promotion program on job stress, stress reactions and coping profiles of women workers: a control groups study. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09769-0>
- Oviatt, D. P., Baumann, M. R., Bennett, J. M., & Garza, R. T. (2017). Undesirable Effects of Working While in College: Work-School Conflict, Substance Use, and Health. *Journal of Psychology: Interdisciplinary and Applied*, 151(5), 433–452. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.2017.1314927>
- Owen, M. S., Kavanagh, P. S., & Dollard, M. F. (2018). An Integrated Model of Work–Study Conflict and Work–Study Facilitation. *Journal of Career Development*, 45(5), 504–517. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845317720071>
- Park, Y., & Sprung, J. M. (2015). Weekly work–school conflict, sleep quality, and fatigue: Recovery self-efficacy as a cross-level moderator. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 36, 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job>
- Peng, Y., Park, Y. A., Su, S., & Ma, J. (2023). Developing and Testing a Model of Dynamic Changes in Work–School Conflict and Workplace Deviance Over Time. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 38(3), 589–605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-022-09841-z>
- Salsabilla, A., Setiawan, M., & Juwita, H. A. J. (2022). The effect of workload and job stress on job satisfaction mediated by work motivation. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), 11(9), 97–106.
- Shukla, A., & Srivastava, R. (2016). Development of short questionnaire to measure

- an extended set of role expectation conflict, coworker support and work-life balance: The new job stress scale. *Cogent Business and Management*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2015.1134034>
- Suh, H., Kim, S. Y., & McCabe, E. A. (2022). Journal of American College Health. *Journal of American College Health*, 70(2), 420–427.
- Wan, M. (Maggie), Feng, L., Meng, X., Zhai, M., & Konopaske, R. (2021). Working College Students' Time Pressure and Work-School Conflict: Do Boundary Permeability and Dispositional Mindfulness Matter? *Psychological Reports*, 125(6), 3100–3125. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00332941211029621>
- Wu, F., Ren, Z., Wang, Q., He, M., Xiong, W., Ma, G., Fan, X., Guo, X., Liu, H., & Zhang, X. (2021). The relationship between job stress and job burnout: the mediating effects of perceived social support and job satisfaction. *Psychology, Health and Medicine*, 26(2), 204–211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2020.1778750>
- Wyland, R. L., Lester, S. W., Mone, M. A., & Winkel, D. E. (2013). Work and school at the same time? A conflict perspective of the work–school interface. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 20(3), 346–357.